

The Centre for Digital Life Norway at Nine Years: Insights from the Legacy Workshop

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Executive summary

From 1–3 April 2025, nearly forty researchers and research-policy professionals met in Trondheim to reflect on the legacy of the Centre for Digital Life Norway (DLN). Now in its tenth year and approaching the end of its second funding period, DLN offers a set of contributions that extend beyond individual projects: new communities, new ways of collaborating, and new forms of support for emerging areas of biotechnology.

Workshop participants described DLN's most visible achievements as the national meeting places it created. Through its annual conferences, research-school activities, and thematic workshops, DLN brought together researchers across institutions, disciplines, and career stages. Junior researchers in particular developed strong cross-institutional networks, while a parallel community formed around questions of interdisciplinarity, responsibility, and the societal role of biotechnology.

DLN also demonstrated that sustained national collaboration is operationally feasible. Its operational team was distributed across NTNU, UiO, and UiB, and collaborated virtually in a matrix structure, predating today's widespread use of virtual teamwork. Several programme components were seen as especially transferable: the seed-funding scheme that catalysed new collaborations; early-stage innovation support that filled a gap between basic research and Technology Transfer Offices; and the national industry-internship programme for PhD candidates, widely viewed as a standout success.

Looking beyond 2026, workshop participants emphasised the need to preserve DLN's relational legacy, including its communities and collaborative ethos, and to strengthen mid-level specialist roles that underpin data-intensive research and innovation.

Discussions also highlighted systemic constraints – limited industrial absorption capacity, short-term academic labour structures, and incentive systems that discourage collaboration – which shape both DLN's legacy and the design of future R&I programmes.

DLN's enduring contribution lies less in a single model than in the environments and practices it enabled, offering valuable insights for Norway's next generation of research and innovation initiatives.

1. Introduction and context

From 1–3 April 2025, nearly forty researchers and research-policy professionals met at the Scandic Nidelven Hotel in Trondheim to reflect on the legacy of the Centre for Digital Life Norway (DLN). Their brief was to clarify which elements of DLN’s ambition merit continuation and how they could be supported in the decade ahead. The atmosphere was collegial and characterised by a sense of reunion; many workshop participants had collaborated across DLN’s nine years of activity.

This report distils the main discussions from the three-day gathering (see Appendix for the programme). It offers a snapshot of DLN in its ninth year – neither an evaluation nor a historical narrative, but a synthesis of perspectives that may inform ongoing debates about the future of biotechnology research and research-funding instruments in Norway.

DLN was established and funded by the Research Council of Norway (RCN) to advance biotechnology research and innovation through national collaboration, Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), and the integration of computational, mathematical, and engineering approaches into biosciences. It is composed of an operational support team – the “network project” – and research projects funded either by RCN under the same programme (default members) or by other sources (affiliate members).

DLN became operational in 2015 with an initial five-year period. In 2020, RCN invited proposals for a second funding period, resulting in DLN2.0 (2021–2026). During its first phase, RCN issued three calls for DLN research projects, funding sixteen projects alongside core support for network operations. These dedicated calls were discontinued in DLN2.0; instead, the Centre expanded its partnership programme, offering access to its services for externally funded projects – reaching around fifty projects by 2024. DLN’s activities are supported by two additional pillars: the Digital Life Norway Research School and the Roadmap for Academic Research-Intensive Innovation.

DLN’s history is marked by co-creation and adaptive planning. The three original network host universities (NTNU, UiO, UiB) worked closely with RCN from the proposal stage onwards. (The institutional partnership eventually grew to also encompass UiT, SINTEF, NMBU, and OUS). This collaborative ethos continued through key moments such as the Selbu conference in 2018 (which used the search-conference method to articulate strategic direction), DLN’s self-evaluation sponsored by RCN in 2019, and multiple research policy dialogues. The 2025 legacy workshop is part of this trajectory of reflective, participatory practice.

Participants in the legacy meeting included members of DLN’s Operational Management Team (OMT), Junior Resource Group (JRG), Expert Task Force (ETF), Steering Board, and Scientific Advisory Board (SAB), alongside affiliated project leaders, RCN representatives, and alumni. Some are directly shaping biotechnology research and innovation in Norway; others contribute to research-policy governance across sectors.

Designed and facilitated by DLN staff with support from Nicole Njå (AFF), the workshop moved from initial legacy reflections to the development of transferable concepts through a combination of plenaries, structured breakout sessions, and targeted keynote inputs.

The workshop did not seek consensus. Participants were asked to:

1. Reflect on DLN's outcomes and legacy; and
2. Identify which aspects of that legacy should be preserved within Norway's research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem and propose pathways for their uptake.

This report is based on notes taken by participants and digital whiteboards on which the participants captured their reflections and analysis *in situ*. The author then collated and synthesised these notes to identify recurring themes and patterns of meaning. The report is thus a co-creation with all the participants. The report is structured as follows: after outlining the workshop and DLN's context, it reconstructs the lived programme theory that emerged from the discussions, summarises what participants viewed as DLN's key contributions, distils elements of its legacy that may warrant preservation, examines possible future configurations, and concludes with broader lessons for the transformation of Norway's research and innovation system.

2. The lived programme theory

Participants engaged in a dual line of reflection. On one level, they examined DLN's achievements and possible futures. In parallel, discussions repeatedly expanded into broader questions about Norwegian research policy: the conditions that enable transformation, and whether DLN's impact can be meaningfully perceived within the current system. This second strand often gravitated toward barriers and missed opportunities – despite the moderator's recurring prompt to first identify concrete changes before analysing the conditions in which they occurred.

A recurrent theme was that a programme of DLN's scale is tightly coupled to its wider policy environment and to the policy imagination of its era. Anne-Kjersti Fahlvik's historical account illustrated this coupling: the Human Genome Project inspired the FUGE programme; international advisers later encouraged the integration of a "digital" component into what became Biotek2021 – an idea considered almost provocative in 2014; and, more recently, national security and defence have become dominant frames shaping biotechnology policy.

Daniel Vonder Mühl's observations from Switzerland reinforced this point: programme ambitions must align with the prevailing political narrative to gain traction. This raised speculative questions about which framing a DLN-like initiative would need today – suggestions ranged from "One Health" and triple-bottom-line perspectives (people, planet, profit) to a "Nansen Centre 2.0" referencing both a national scientific icon and a previous interdisciplinary research programme of that name.

The frequently repeated statement that “DLN couldn’t happen anymore today” was discussed as an indicator of how policy conditions had changed. Several participants argued that DLN’s formative period was shaped by RCN’s former willingness to experiment with policy formats: publishing a white paper articulating a vision for DLN, organising mutual-learning activities, and engaging with ideas from third-generation innovation policy focused on addressing societal challenges through research. Since roughly 2017, participants felt that RCN has deprioritised this developmental role, becoming “an empty vessel” that channels funding but invests less in policy learning. Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), they argued, is disappearing from the agenda. This raised a broader question: does RCN still have the institutional capacity to learn from DLN as a policy experiment?

Another strand of discussion examined the claim that “DLN was not as visible as it could have been.” Participants debated whether this critique reflects DLN’s limitations in signalling its achievements, or RCN’s limited capacity to perceive impacts that do not fit conventional performance indicators. One participant invoked Gramsci’s remark that “history teaches, but has no pupils,” interpreting the situation as a possible case of strategic attention scarcity within funding organisations. The group also reflected on whether “visibility” is an adequate lens at all, given that some forms of influence – such as shifts in attitudes or collaboration cultures – are inherently difficult to observe from the outside.

DLN was widely understood as a structure for national collaboration. Participants pointed to examples where its organisational model had already been replicated or considered elsewhere: the research centre AFINO adopted a similar structure, and the national AI Centre programme debated – but did not ultimately adopt – the model. At the legacy meeting, NTNU’s rector Tor Grande described DLN as a mechanism that helps reconcile competitive project-based funding with the need for coordinated national efforts, such as the upcoming “Polarhavet 2050” programme. (Svein Stølen, rector of the University of Oslo, has also publicly endorsed the DLN model.)

At the same time, when the question “What problem is DLN actually a solution to?” was raised, participants voiced multiple, co-existing interpretations. One participant privately noted that it felt as though several parallel conversations were occurring, each with different stakeholders in mind. The interpretations included:

- A forum for addressing “big questions” and aligning research agendas with societal needs. Here, concepts such as the polycrisis, third-generation innovation policy, and the need for reflective space were central. One RRI adviser described his role with the metaphor of an Ent – the slow-speaking, long-lived trees from Tolkien – anchoring discussions in very long-term perspectives.
- A programme to position biotechnology as a national asset for a post-oil economy.
- An initiative to expand capacity in mathematical model-driven biosciences, including the foundations for data-intensive approaches.

- A pilot addressing the “valley of death” in the innovation system, by assessing early innovation potential and offering targeted coaching to research projects.

Taken together, these perspectives illustrate that DLN’s lived programme theory was plural and layered: a combination of scientific, societal, infrastructural, and innovation-oriented ambitions, understood differently across participant groups and institutional backgrounds.

3. DLN’s key contributions

Participants reflected on DLN’s impacts both in a series of online pre-meetings as well as during the workshop itself. The term “impact” was used in a broad, non-technical sense – not according to formal evaluation logic models that distinguish outputs, outcomes, and impacts. Several participants emphasised that DLN’s full effects may not yet be visible, and that attribution is intrinsically difficult: DLN operated within wider scientific and policy trends such as data-intensive biology, integration of modelling into biosciences, and the evolution of Norway’s innovation system.

Two cautions were raised. First, visibility bias: discrete programmes are easier to recognise than subtle shifts in collaboration cultures, perspectives, or research practices. Second, attribution bias: DLN did not initiate trends such as omics adoption or research “datafication,” but may have influenced how these developments unfolded within Norway.

The impacts described by participants are summarised below, ordered by decreasing institutional complexity.

DLN established national meeting places and distinct communities

DLN’s annual conferences, research-school courses, and thematic workshops (such as the Modelling Living Systems series) created durable national meeting places. Three communities were repeatedly highlighted:

1. **A community centred on modelling, bioinformatics, and systems-oriented biotechnology**

Participants described this as a “techno-epistemic” community that developed shared practices around tools, modelling methodologies, and theoretical aspects of data-intensive biosciences. The Modelling Living Systems workshop series was seen as particularly formative.

2. **A community of junior researchers**

DLN pre- and postdoctoral researchers developed a strong shared identity through their participation in annual conferences and the courses offered by the Research School. These included not only technical courses but also bespoke offerings such as the transdisciplinarity and RRI courses. The formal representation of junior researchers in both the Research School and DLN governance – through the Junior Resource Group (JRG) – was also seen as important for building this community.

Participants described this community as particularly valuable for junior researchers involved in the sixteen projects funded during DLN's first funding period. At the same time, many Research School members were not affiliated with DLN-funded projects, and some participated despite limited support – or even explicit opposition – from their supervisors, underscoring both the independent motivation of these researchers and the perceived value of DLN's offerings.

3. A transformational community

This group convened around deeper questions of interdisciplinary research, the societal purpose of biotechnology, and research governance. Participants noted that DLN offered more sophisticated conversations about inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration than those typically found in their home environments.

DLN demonstrated that sustained national collaboration is operationally feasible

The DLN "network project" maintained a matrix organisation with staff employed across three universities and multiple faculties. Years before the COVID-19 pandemic normalised distributed teams, the Operational Management Team (OMT) already operated as a functional remote collaboration. Participants emphasised that this arrangement helped circumvent administrative barriers that often impede interdisciplinary work – even within single institutions. DLN thus served as a working proof-of-concept for national-scale organisational collaboration in the life sciences.

DLN catalysed collaborative research through its seed-funding programme

Following the 2018 Selbu meeting, DLN launched a low-threshold seed-funding scheme to stimulate collaboration among its affiliated projects. Participants described the programme as successful in initiating partnerships, some of which matured into full research-funding applications. The model was also seen as a conceptual precursor to RCN's later "Collaborative and Knowledge-building Project" funding mechanism.

DLN filled a niche in the national innovation system

DLN's innovation support activities – early-stage coaching, identification of innovation potential, and facilitation of industry partnerships – were perceived as operating in a space not covered by existing structures. Positioned between basic research and the technology-readiness levels (TRLs) typically handled by university Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs), DLN helped shift perceptions of innovation towards a mindset rather than a discrete stage. The University of Oslo's Growth House was cited as an example of a later initiative that drew inspiration from DLN's approach.

DLN increased recognition of data management as expert labour

Participants emphasised the invisible but essential work required to make biological data usable for modelling and aligned with FAIR principles. DLN helped spotlight data management, research software engineering, and related forms of expert labour that are frequently undervalued but foundational for progress in data-intensive biosciences. The discussions highlighted the gap between idealised visions of standardised data practices and the complex organisational and technical realities encountered in daily work.

The industry internship programme created a unique national opportunity

DLN's industry-internship scheme allows PhD candidates to spend several months working in Norwegian life-science companies while remaining employed by their home universities. Funded through DLN and administered via home institutions, the programme was widely regarded as a flagship initiative: unique in Norway, consistently praised by participating students, and illustrative of DLN's ability to overcome significant bureaucratic challenges (including intellectual-property and state-aid concerns). Participants viewed the internships as one of DLN's most concrete and transferable contributions.

DLN had lasting personal impact on individual researchers

Many participants believed that involvement in DLN leaves enduring personal and professional traces. One formerly junior researcher described a trajectory from wet-lab science to engagement with the societal dimensions of research, to a later career in research support. While not generalisable to all members, such narratives capture a broader theme: DLN created conditions for individuals to explore new roles, perspectives, and career pathways.

4. What to carry forward

The following synthesis distils the elements of DLN's legacy that participants considered worth preserving. No ranking or voting took place during the workshop; these points reflect recurring themes rather than prioritised recommendations.

- **Strengthen the societal purpose of biotechnology research.**
Participants cautioned against reducing scientific transformation to purely technological or methodological questions. DLN's emphasis on responsibility, reflection, and societal anchoring was widely viewed as worth sustaining.
- **Preserve DLN's relational legacy: "DLN is really about the people."**
The communities that emerged through DLN – across disciplines, institutions, and career stages – were seen as one of its most valuable contributions. Any successor

structure should retain the collaborative and cross-institutional spaces that DLN cultivated.

- **Maintain and grow the community of practice.**

As a new generation of researchers moves into leadership roles, participants argued that DLN's culture of openness, interdisciplinarity, and peer support should be preserved and embedded in future initiatives.

- **Professionalise research-adjacent and 3rd space roles in the research system.**

Roles such as data stewards, innovation advisers, research coordinators, and research-software or computational specialists were repeatedly described as essential infrastructure. Participants emphasised the need for stable career paths and recognition for these roles.

- **Ensure institutional support for interdisciplinary and non-traditional educational models.**

DLN's Research School and training activities were valued for exposing students to multiple disciplines, methods, and perspectives. Sustaining such formats requires explicit commitment from universities.

- **Bolster support for mid-stage innovation (TRL 4–6).**

Participants highlighted a persistent gap between basic research and technology-transfer offices. Sustained funding and support mechanisms for early translational stages were viewed as essential for realising biotechnology's potential.

Because funding for a "DLN 3.0" seemed unlikely, participants explored alternative configurations for maintaining these legacies.

5. Possible future setups

Participants discussed several potential pathways to carry forward elements of the DLN model. The scenarios below are exploratory rather than prescriptive; no consensus emerged.

Scenario A: A minimal, membership-based structure

One pragmatic suggestion was to establish a lean association to preserve DLN's core relational functions – networking, thematic workshops, training, and peer support. The model would involve:

- A coordinator (potentially part-time),
- An annual budget of approximately NOK 2 million,
- Institutional memberships from universities, contributing either financially or through staff time.

Participants noted, however, that membership models often struggle without strong local champions and sustained institutional buy-in. Experience suggests that universities may sign up on paper but under-utilise the network in practice.

Scenario B: Coordinated devolution to universities

Another scenario involved distributing DLN's functional components across the host universities. Each university would assume lead responsibility for one domain (e.g., data and models, innovation, or training). This model resembles a "federated" continuation of DLN.

Its feasibility was questioned: successful implementation would require explicit leadership-level commitments and clear mandates within institutions. Reported interest in, for example, continuing the industry-internship programme was limited.

Scenario C: Bottom-up continuation through researcher-led initiatives

A more organic, decentralised option envisioned researchers themselves continuing thematic working groups or communities of practice. This approach would depend on available time, intrinsic motivation, and alignment with career incentives – factors participants judged to be unevenly distributed across the system.

Scenario D: Transfer of specific programmes to existing organisations

Participants also identified opportunities to transfer components:

- **Innovation activities** to Technology Transfer Offices or UiO's Growth House;
- **Data and modelling practices** to structures such as ELIXIR Norway;
- **Research-school activities** to existing national research schools.

This scenario emphasised integration into established infrastructures rather than maintaining a distinct DLN-branded entity.

6. Learnings about transformation in research and innovation

Participants examined DLN's implicit ("lived") theory of change: the expectation that networked, interdisciplinary knowledge production would generate societal and economic value. They identified several assumptions and systemic constraints that complicate this narrative.

Assumption 1: Limited absorption capacity in domestic industry

Norway's strongest industrial pull on academic research still comes from the fossil-fuel and aquaculture sectors. A robust domestic biofabrication or biotechnology industry has not yet emerged. As a result, innovation-push programmes face structural limits: without sufficient industry-side demand or absorption capacity, research-driven innovations struggle to find pathways beyond proof-of-concept. Participants questioned the applicability of international examples (e.g., Denmark), given differences in industrial history and market structures.

Assumption 2: Temporal instability within academia

Short-term contracts for PhDs, postdocs, and project staff create a highly transient workforce. DLN itself experienced frequent turnover, including four operational directors, and NTNU saw three rectors during DLN's lifespan. RCN also underwent structural and personnel changes. Participants referred to this as a pervasive "project logic": institutions rely on short-term labour, undermining continuity, institutional memory, and long-term responsibility. As Ulrike Felt noted, responsibility is inherently temporal, defined by who holds it, when, and for how long.

Assumption 3: Institutional anchoring remained aspirational

At the Selbu meeting in 2018, DLN articulated the goal of becoming institutionally anchored in its host universities. Participants at the legacy workshop concluded that this anchoring was never realised. When the question of concrete steps taken to secure such anchoring arose, the group did not identify follow-through. Universities tended to treat DLN as a project rather than an institutional responsibility.

Assumption 4: DLN functioned as an open, voluntary system

DLN operated through a "coalition of the willing." Participation could not be mandated; trust had to be built over time. Early-career researchers were consistently over-represented in DLN's active community. Engaging senior researchers proved more difficult, attributed partly to incentive structures that reward individual competition – "innovate or die" – over time-intensive collaboration and care work.

Assumption 5: Interdisciplinary group dynamics are shaped by belonging

Interdisciplinary collaboration brings together different epistemic cultures. Participants observed that individuals sometimes self-censored or aligned with dominant disciplinary norms to maintain legitimacy and secure group belonging. These dynamics are not unique

to DLN but complicate the transfer of genuinely innovative or boundary-crossing ideas across institutional and disciplinary boundaries.

Assumption 6: Visibility is a weak indicator of transformation

Participants warned that visibility should not be equated with impact. Omics, modelling, and data-intensive research are now ubiquitous, but the unglamorous expert labour enabling these practices remains low-profile. They also noted a growing phenomenon of researchers “speaking policy” – using phrases such as “RRI is of course important” – without necessarily integrating the underlying principles into practice. This kind of rhetorical compliance can obscure whether deeper transformation has occurred.

7. Conclusion

DLN’s legacy emerges as a combination of people, practices, and institutional experiments. Across the workshop discussions, participants consistently emphasised three intertwined strands: a relational legacy centred on community; a set of operational structures that demonstrated the feasibility of national collaboration; and a body of “transformation wisdom” that speaks to broader challenges in Norway’s research and innovation (R&I) system.

This report has synthesised these perspectives without aiming for consensus. The workshop format foregrounded plurality rather than convergence. As a result, the findings should be interpreted as a composite of situated viewpoints rather than a unified assessment. Importantly, the discussions drew primarily on the experiences of those who have participated in DLN; voices from outside the programme, including industry partners, non-participating research groups, or senior university leadership beyond the immediate DLN network, were not systematically represented. The workshop also did not attempt to reconstruct DLN’s full operational history or scientific output. These limitations shape the report’s scope: it provides insight into perceived legacies, institutional learnings, and systemic constraints, not a comprehensive evaluation.

The discussions surfaced several lessons for leaders shaping Norway’s R&I landscape – rectors, research-council officers, policy designers, and others. Participants highlighted the importance of maintaining institutional spaces where interdisciplinary collaboration, reflective practice, and long-term thinking can occur. They also noted structural constraints that inhibit such spaces: short project cycles, unstable staffing, limited industrial absorption capacity, and the persistent tension between competitive individual incentives and the relational work of collaboration. Addressing these challenges will require coordinated action at multiple levels: universities need to create durable mid-level roles and recognise the labour of coordination and data management; funders need to maintain policy-learning capacities and support mid-stage innovation; and programme

designers need to ensure that new initiatives align with contemporary policy framings without losing sight of scientific and societal purpose.

DLN's legacy does not lie in a single structure or model. Rather, it resides in the practices it enabled, the communities it convened, and the perspectives it brought into view. The programme demonstrated that national collaboration is both possible and fragile; that responsibility and innovation require time, continuity, and expert labour; and that meaningful transformation occurs not only through technological advances but through gradual shifts in culture, roles, and shared understandings.

As DLN approaches its conclusion, the question is not whether it will be continued in its current form, but which of its practices and insights should inform Norway's next generation of research and innovation initiatives. This report suggests that DLN's most enduring contribution may be its generative effect: creating conditions in which new communities, roles, and ways of thinking could emerge. Carrying this legacy forward will require sustained commitment from institutions and individuals alike – but the workshop made clear that the foundations exist for such work to continue.

Appendix: Meeting programme

1 April 2025

09.30	Mingling
10.00	Welcome & warm up Day 1
11.00	Introduction with Anne Kjersti Fahlvik (NFR)
11.45	Break
12.00	Where we started and how Digital Life Norway developed with Trygve Brautaset (NTNU)
12.30	Lunch
13.30	Where we started and how Digital Life Norway developed – cont.
14.00	What has DLN changed?
15.15	Break
15.30	Biotechnology innovation challenges and opportunities: past, presentation and future
17.00	End of workday 1

2 April 2025

09.00	Recap & Day 2
09.30	Responsible research & innovation with Ulrike Felt (Uni Wien)
10.00	Break
10.15	Group work parallel sessions: RRI in biotechnology; DLN partnerships; Interdisciplinarity; What happened to the “Digital” in DLN?
12.00	Lunch
13.00	Walk & talks
13.45	Presentation with Tor Grande
14.15	Group work related to training of the next generation of biotechnology professionals
15.15	Norwegian biotechnology future scenarios
17.00	End of workday 2

3 April 2025

09.00	Recap and Day 3
09.30	Looking forward: Where is Norwegian biotech heading in the next decade? What can we learn from previous initiatives? with Daniel Vonder Mühll (ETH Zurich)
10.00	Group work and dialogue on various future scenarios
11.20	Wrap up
12.00	End of workshop & lunch